

Dependence Structure of the Vietnam Stock Market on the International Stock Market

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Abstract

Background: The deep and broad integration of Vietnam's economy with the world economy brings opportunities and challenges in sustainable economic development. In light of the risk of global financial crises significantly impacting the national economy, implementing a sustainable stock market development strategy has become extremely necessary.

Objective: The goal was to examine the impact of Vietnam's stock market's dependence structure on the international stock market, thereby providing policy implications for a more stable and sustainable development of Vietnam's stock market.

Methodology: This article examines the dependence structure between the Vietnamese stock market and international stock markets, utilising research data collected from January 2007 to December 2024 and employing the Monte Carlo simulation method.

Result: The results show that during the COVID period, the level of dependence of the Vietnamese stock market on the international stock market was higher than in other periods. The results indicate that the selected copula is most appropriate for capturing the dependency structure between the Vietnamese and international stock markets. The article also calculates the value at risk using the Monte Carlo simulation method, demonstrating that an investment portfolio in the Vietnamese stock market under the negative impact of the US market has the highest risk level compared to other markets.

Conclusion: The model demonstrates that the Copula function is suitable for financial market pairs.

Unique Contribution: This study develops an early warning system for the financial market, playing a significant role in helping state management agencies estimate and calculate the likelihood of a crisis, understand the factors that can lead to such a situation, and enable them to react and make appropriate adjustments when the economy undergoes unfavourable changes.

Key Recommendation: Based on the research results, several essential policy implications are proposed to develop an early warning system that also enables state management agencies to assess

the impact of macroeconomic policies on the likelihood of a crisis, thereby evaluating the effectiveness of these policies on the stock market.

Keywords: Stock market; policy implications; international stock market; Vietnam.

Introduction

The nature of the connection between states is a hotly contested issue in light of the world's growing economic and political integration. The last 30 years have seen much focus on economic globalisation compared to the other two components of globalisation, political and social (Alp et al., 2021). The world's stock markets are starting to work together, at least in theory. If the stock market in one country is in shock, it could cause volatility in another country's market. The Vietnamese stock market reflects important domestic economic and political indicators (VNIndex). Researching how the Vietnamese stock market is linked to global stock markets is thus an important and pertinent topic.

This study chooses stock markets from various parts of the world rankings to obtain a thorough grasp of the dependency structure between VNIndex and international markets. Notably, we take a look at the two biggest stock markets on the planet, the S&P 500 index in the US and the NIKKEI index in Japan, as well as four major Asian stock markets, namely the TWII index in Taiwan, the SSCE index in China, the STI index in Singapore, and the KOSPI index in South Korea. In addition to reflecting national economies, these chosen indicators show patterns in the world's two most important economic areas, Asia and the United States, which drive economic growth (Kartal et al., 2022). With this selection, you can see how global and regional financial situations affect Vietnam. Thus, the study's objective is to consider the impact of the dependence structure of Vietnam's stock market on the international stock market, thereby giving policy implications for more stable and sustainable development of Vietnam's stock market.

Literature Review

Research on the interdependence structure of the Vietnamese and international stock markets has garnered much interest from scholars in the context of economic integration and globalization. The impact of volatility transmission from the US to the Vietnamese stock market was investigated (Chancharat & Chancharat, 2024). This study uses the VAR-DCC-GARCH model in conjunction with quantile regression. The study utilized weekly returns of stock indexes. Findings from the article's research indicate that the return rate of the US stock market influences the Vietnamese stock market favorably. Positive and quantile-specific volatility transmission from the US stock market to Vietnam is more precise. During the period of 2017–2023, when the global economic context was unstable due to events such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the conflict between Russia and Ukraine, Banda et al. (2019) utilized the quantile vector autoregression (QVAR) and spillover index methods to examine the relationship and spillover level of the US and ASEAN stock markets, as well as other stock markets, including India, Japan, South Korea, and China. In the face of highly volatile markets, the findings reveal a spillover impact from the markets of the United States, South Korea, and Singapore to other markets. Using quantile-quantile regression (QQR), Arshad et al. (2024) examined the impact of US monetary policy on frontier and emerging stock markets in Asia, encompassing Vietnam, from 2006 to 2022.

The study indicated that when market circumstances are dire, there is a stronger negative correlation between US monetary policy uncertainty and stock market indices. From 2005 to 2009, Mohti et al. (2019) examined the ripple effect on frontier stock markets, such as Vietnam's, from the US stock market. Utilizing the conditional copula model (Copula-GARCH), the research discovered a weak tail dependence between the US stock market and frontier markets, indicating that these markets may be suitable options for diversification techniques in a portfolio. The dependence structure between the US and Vietnam stock markets from 2006 to 2020 was examined by Aluko & Kolapo (2019) using the conditional copula model (Copula-GJR-GARCH). With relatively little tail reliance present, the results demonstrated that the Clayton copula best characterized the structure of tail dependency between the two markets. By extending previous studies on cryptocurrency dependency structures, Arshad et al. (2024) demonstrate the viability of using the conditional copula model (Copula-GJR-GARCH) to examine the interdependencies between various financial assets. According to this research, the Vietnamese stock market is impacted by regional and developed markets, including the United States, Japan, and Korea.

Theoretical Framework

Many methods exist to measure the dependence of financial data series. However, these methods assume that the data series are linearly correlated or have a normal distribution. For example, the extended GARCH model methods such as ARMA-GARCH, APGARCH, EGARCH, TGARCH, FIGARCH, DCC-GARCH, and CCC-GARCH all assume that the data series should follow this pattern. Because of its inherent volatility and unpredictability, the financial market does not adequately represent the assumptions made in these methodologies. To get around the problems with the above methods, people often employ the unconditional copula method, which is based on Ciftci et al. (2019). Benefits of using the copula function to describe the dependence relationship between financial asset return series include modeling the dependence when market fluctuations are normal and the tail dependence of the distribution function when market fluctuations are incredibly extreme, and not assuming that the probability distribution of the return series is normally distributed (Chen et al., 2014). According to some research, the failure to account for the time-varying nature of financial return series is why unconditional copula is inappropriate. By considering the tail dependence at the same time as the fluctuation of financial asset returns over time, the GARCH-copula is the best method for describing the dependence structure between financial markets. This method can describe both symmetric and asymmetric dependence structures, and it reflects the leverage effect in risk assessment in the event of a market collapse (Hasan et al., 2021).

Give Z_1 và Z_2 là 2 random variable has a normal distribution, with a conditional marginal distribution function u và v tức là $F_1(z_1|\Omega_{t-1}) = u, F_2(z_2|\Omega_{t-1}) = v$. Let H be the conditional simultaneous distribution function as follows $H(z_1, z_2|\Omega_{t-1}) = P(Z_1 \leq z_1, Z_2 \leq z_2|\Omega_{t-1})$. With Ω_{t-1} is a collection containing information up to a point in time $t-1$. Then there exists only one conditional Copula function $C: [0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ with

$$H(z_1, z_2|\Omega_{t-1}) = C(u, v|\Omega_{t-1})$$

Conversely, if C is a conditional two-variable copula and F_1 and F_2 are two conditional distribution functions. Then, the function H is a conditional simultaneous distribution function with the conditional marginal distribution functions, respectively, $F_1(z_1|\Omega_{t-1}), F_2(z_2|\Omega_{t-1})$.

Any copula can merge several marginal distributions into a valid joint probability distribution. This affords us some leeway when dealing with financial data series, as they all have different marginal distribution functions. On the other hand, we can combine them with a family of copulas to get a joint probability distribution function, which is a great outcome and gives us a handy tool for looking at two time series at once. Copula functions are commonly used to find the asymmetric dependence structure between financial asset return series when the market varies at extreme margins since they allow modeling tail reliance (Keswani et al., 2024).

Give Z_1 và Z_2 là 2 continuous random variable has a marginal distribution function of F_1, F_2 The coefficient depends on the upper tail $\lambda_u = \lim_{u \rightarrow 1} P(Z_1 > F_1^{-1}(u) | Z_2 > F_2^{-1}(u)) = \lim_{u \rightarrow 1} \frac{1 - 2u + C(u,v)}{1 - u}$

Lower tail dependence coefficient $\lambda_L = \lim_{u \rightarrow 1} P(Z_1 < F_1^{-1}(u) | Z_2 < F_2^{-1}(u)) = \lim_{u \rightarrow 1} \frac{C(u,v)}{1 - u}$

If $\lambda_u = 0$ then we say there is no tailed dependency on the if $\lambda_u \in (0,1]$ is copula C There are upper tail dependencies, similarly for the lower tail.

The significance of a subset of Copula functions Under typical circumstances, the symmetrical structure of the Gaussian Copula family exhibits correlation. The two markets will behave independently of one another when market fluctuations occur, and the random variables are around their mean values in this scenario. Asymmetrical in both tails, the Student and Frank Copula families are similar. While Student-t demonstrates correlation in calm markets, it depends on the other market regardless of price changes when market volatility is high. The degree of reliance increases as the degrees of freedom (df) decrease.

When market volatility is present, the Frank family exhibits correlation; when price fluctuations occur, the two markets continue to rely on one another. Rot-Joe Copula, Rot-Gumbel, and Clayton are all asymmetrical families with skewed lower tails. During bear markets, they exhibit correlation; asset Y will fall much more steeply if asset X declines. The interdependence between the two markets' potential collapse increases as the dependence coefficient grows. In contrast, families like Rot Joe, BB6, BB8, and Gumbel are symmetrical and top-heavy. Under rising market conditions, they reflect correlation; a more considerable increase in X is accompanied by a more significant rise in Y. Two markets experiencing rapid growth will have greater reliance if their coefficients are more important. Finally, the lower tails of the BB1 and BB7 families are asymmetrical. When X and Y are both highly volatile, they exhibit correlation, meaning that Y will respond in tandem to a sudden drop (or rise) in X. Two markets are more likely to decline (increase) in tandem if their dependence coefficients are more extensive in the lower (upper) tails.

Research Methods

Research data

Aims to measure the dependence structure between the Vietnamese and international stock markets. The study collects time series data with daily frequency during the period from January 2, 2007, to November 30, 2024, of stock markets including the US (S&P 500), Vietnam (VNI), Japan (Nikkei 225), Korea (Kospi), Singapore (STI), China (SSCE), Taiwan (TWII). The return rate series of stock markets is calculated according to the formula: $r_{i,t} = [\ln(P_{i,t}) - \ln(P_{i,t-1})] \times 100$. With: $P_{i,t}$ và $P_{i,t-1}$ are the price of market i at time t and at time t - 1, respectively. Profit rates of stock markets.

Data processing and analysis methods

The following are the precise steps to follow to analyze the reliance structure of the Vietnamese stock market on worldwide stock markets:

Step 1: The authors need to estimate some models for the marginal distribution and then choose the best one using the minimal AIC information criterion. Second, convert the GJR-GARCH model's residuals into a probability distribution and use the following tests to ensure that the marginal distribution model is suitable: (i) the Anderson-Darling (AD) test,

Step 2: The Cramer-von Mis (Cv-M) test, and

Step 3: The Kolmogorov-Smornov (KS) test. The authors determine the conditional copula parameters for two types of market volatility: high volatility (Archimedean copulas) and low volatility (Gaussian, Student, and Frank families). To find the best conditional copula model, compare all proposed models using the AIC information criterion.

Step 4: The authors applied the Copula function parameters calculated in Step 3 using the Monte Carlo simulation approach with a 95% confidence level to determine the Value at Risk (VaR) value.

Model for marginal distributions autocorrelation, volatility clustering, asymmetric effects, and distribution shape are some profit rate series characteristics modeled in the GJR-GARCH model (Thomas et al., 2022; Glosten et al., 1993). Here is the ARMA(p,q)-GJR-GARCH(m,k) model:

Average equation:

$$r_t = \mu + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i r_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j e_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \tag{1}$$

Variance equation:

$$h_t = \sigma_t^2 = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i \varepsilon_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j \sigma_{t-1}^2 + \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i I_{t-i} \varepsilon_{t-i}^2 \tag{2}$$

With: μ is the blocking constant; δ_i is the autoregressive parameter of the stationary series at time $t - i$; θ_j is the moving average parameter with e_{t-j} is the error of time t and time $t - j$. $\varepsilon_t = \sqrt{h_t} z_t$ is the remainder with z_t is the residual normalized by the shape of the distribution; $\sigma_t = \sqrt{h_t}$ is the standard deviation conditional on time t ; parameter ARCH(α) and GARCH(β) denote that the standard deviation is influenced by past variance and standard deviation; γ is the asymmetric parameter (leverage), I_t is a dummy variable and $I_t = 1$ when $\varepsilon_t < 0$ và $I_t = 0$ in the remaining cases (Cherubini et al., 2004).

Study Results

According to Table 1's descriptive statistics, the world's two biggest stock markets - the US (SP500) and Japan (NIKKEN) had positive average returns before the COVID pandemic hit, suggesting that these markets were well-established. At this time, the US Federal Reserve (Fed) and the Bank of Japan adopted loose monetary policies to prop up the economy. The market rose

because of the robust growth of many significant technological businesses, including Apple, Amazon, and Google. In contrast to large markets like the US (SP500) and Japan (NIKKEN), the Vietnamese stock market has experienced more challenges, as indicated by its negative return rate.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Before Covid 2007-12/2019							
	VNI	SP500	NIKKEN	SSCE	KOPSI	STI	TWII
Mean	-0.0064	0.0312	0.0138	-0.0128	0.0111	-0.0043	0.0088
Min	10.3509	10.4074	45.1225	9.0343	11.2844	18.6432	64.5172
Max	-10.9316	-13.7757	-45.8071	-12.7636	-11.1720	-10.6280	-52.9218
Standard deviation	1.6370	1.4225	6.0957	1.8960	1.4301	1.3086	6.7715
Jarque-Bera	2424.238***	14425.86***	19591.65***	2471.77***	8149.85***	57422.78***	70689.55***
ADF	-28.8468***	-52.5224***	-16.6093***	-47.1365***	-47.7517***	-47.3241***	-16.4215***
ARCH(2)	56.2047***	208.0663***	69.9199***	44.7767***	75.1926***	16.1340***	40.6413***
N	2,330	2,330	2,330	2,330	2,330	2,330	2,330
During Covid 1/2020-6/2022							
Mean	0.0696	0.0530	0.0427	0.0291	0.0344	0.0015	0.0727
Min	6.3781	9.9840	20.7698	7.9213	8.2513	6.0947	31.7617
Max	-8.5295	-10.1863	-45.5418	-5.5391	-8.7670	-7.0712	-36.3463
Standard deviation	1.7997	1.7993	4.9812	1.3036	1.6151	1.3064	6.1680
Jarque-Bera	531.2068***	1137.539***	7723.631***	492.664***	545.7736***	771.1373***	1235.753***
ADF	-18.6709***	-22.4278***	-14.2226***	-19.8018***	-18.0929***	-17.7396***	-11.4442***
ARCH(2)	11.0035***	29.3549***	34.9442***	20.9186***	45.9182***	46.2553***	27.2043***
N	423	423	423	423	423	423	423
After Covid 6/2022-now							
Mean	0.0091	0.1017	0.0820	-0.0037	0.0051	0.0409	0.0837
Min	5.3902	3.8538	23.2515	7.7551	6.0033	3.1052	34.5180
Max	-11.7902	-6.2768	-26.2766	-4.1368	-12.6463	-6.3389	-27.2474
Standard deviation	1.4087	1.1244	4.9508	1.1432	1.3810	0.8197	5.4333
Jarque-Bera	3003.979***	149.580***	1322.567***	686.138***	5401.375***	1513.5011***	1425.3381***
ADF	-21.8890***	-20.8096***	-12.8346***	-19.4167***	-23.5470***	-19.6392***	-13.1496***
ARCH(2)	3.4595***	7.4566***	11.8963***	19.8559***	3.1218***	17.0441***	4.9637***
N	429	429	429	429	429	429	429

Source: Authors' calculations

*Note: *** represents the level of statistical significance of 1%.*

Table 2: Results of estimating marginal distribution model parameters

Before Covid 2007-2019							
Part A. Average equation							
	μ	φ_1	φ_2	θ_1	θ_2		
SP500	0.125247***	1.067***	-0.16***	-1.132***	0.208***		
VNINDEX	0.089113***	0.600233***	-0.477201**				
SSCE	0.044809***	-0.000065**					
Nikken	0.046086***	0.639924***	0.055539***	-0.818916***			
KOPSI	0.053030***	0.525854***	-0.926913**	-0.516372***	0.951239***		
STI	0.046169***	0.023087***	-0.001062**				
TWII	0.062661***	1.557714***	-0.585069*	-1.580147***	0.598973***		
Part B. Variance equation							
	ω	α_1	α_2	β_1	β_2	γ_1	γ_2
SP500	0.0279***	0.19755***	0.1231**	0.829***		-0.2017***	-0.0827***
VNINDEX	0.036108***	0.181410***		0.870275***		-0.105371*	
SSCE	0.013000***	0.05364***	0.033611***	0.937511***		-0.083971*	0.028606***
Nikken	6.218829***	0.908413***	0.185313***	0.148939***		-0.272367*	-0.214963
KOPSI	0.015963***	0.122905***		0.937353***		-0.126370*	
STI	0.017463***	0.214482***		0.198227***	0.693733***	-0.214884*	
TWII	0.255615***	0.045372***	0.000202***	0.966457***		0.358129***	-0.39440**
During Covid 2020-2022							
Part A. Average equation							
	μ	φ_1	φ_2	θ_1	θ_2		
SP500	0.145297***	1.912372*	-0.912564	-1.986909	0.986387		
VNINDEX	0.240447***	-0.373510	-0.9908***	0.362***	1.0040***		
SSCE	0.050224***	1.104331*	-0.977993	1.124784	1.008669		
Nikken	0.024726	0.347346	0.26577***	-0.5827***	-0.2003***		
KOPSI	0.038259***	0	0	0.084195	0		
STI	0.073612***	0.09617***	-0.081720	0	0		
TWII	0.069292	-0.170453	0.806945	0.104997	-0.8641***		
Part B. Variance equation							
	ω	α_1	α_2	β_1	β_2	γ_1	γ_2
SP500	0.058285***	0.334292**	0.000000	0.812901	0.000000	-0.296385*	0
VNINDEX	0.161952***	0.358501*	0.000000	0.814737	0.000000	-0.29209**	-0.056382
SSCE	0.0008315***	0.000104**	0.000051**	0.019652**	0.994032**	0.02715***	-0.05692**
Nikken	4.266660***	1.000000*	0.719976	0.000000	0.000000	-0.69144**	-0.676155*
KOPSI	0.180215***	0.216230*	0.173109***	0.000000	0.738422***	-0.11086**	-0.255627
STI	0.2551***	0.437867**	0.040135	0.000000	0.462336***	0.010383	-0.129948
TWII	5.284965***	1.000000***	0.000000	0.293758***	0	-0.804896	-0.00146**
After Covid 2022 – Now							
Part A. Average equation							
	μ	φ_1	φ_2	θ_1	θ_2		
SP500	0.165607***	1.337975***	-0.995698*	-1.349981*	0.997280***		
VNINDEX	0.122477**	0	0	0.049092***	0.094542***		
SSCE	-0.007103	0.974766***	0	-1.032251*	0.040206***		
Nikken	0.120127***	0.774766***	0	-0.834489	0		
KOPSI	0.021890***	-0.106043*	0.634676***	0.065294**	-0.551057*		
STI	0.044440	0.738777***	-0.986648*	-0.719618*	1.002676***		
TWII	0.149938***	0.848835***	0	-0.881868*	0		
Part B. Variance equation							
	ω	α_1	α_2	β_1	β_2	γ_1	γ_2
SP500	0.008735***	0.137929**	0	0.942885***	0	-0.150298*	0
VNINDEX	0.071834***	0.263724***	0	0.851264***	0	-0.231975*	0
SSCE	0.303891**	0.334133***	0	0.017266***	0.492329*	-0.199111**	0
Nikken	0.156659***	0.037544***	0.001569	0.996925	0	0.429522***	-0.506235
KOPSI	0.110670*	0.075180***	0	0.907379	0	-0.096728*	0
STI	0.002566*	0.000000	0	1.000000***	0	-0.006988	0
TWII	0.157116*	0.004574***	0.000001	0.999999	0	0.978475	-0.999828

Source: Author's calculations

Table 1 & 2 increased reliance during COVID-19, indicating that Vietnam was more vulnerable to shocks from outside sources, especially Asian markets. Nevertheless, according to VaR95%, the US market was not the most exposed to risk during this time. In the post-COVID era, Asian markets continue to have an influence despite reducing dependence on the United States. The coefficient fell from 0.1185 to 0.04 in the post-COVID era, indicating a considerable reduction in the reliance of the Vietnamese stock market on the American market. As a result, Vietnam's sustained financial integration with regional markets is indicated by the relatively high dependency on major Asian stock markets ($\delta > 0.2$). Although reliance on the US decreased, the VaR95% results suggest that risk exposure to the US market was highest during this time.

Under less volatile market conditions

Table 3: Model parameter estimation results for Copula-GJR-GARCH in highly volatile market conditions

Before Covid 2007-2019							
Market	Copula	AIC	δ	λ_L	λ_U	τ	VaR 95%
VNI/SP500	Student-t	-50.595	0.04	0.0317	0.0317	0.026	0.294
VNI/NIKKEN	Student-t	-54.528	0.11	0.02	0.02	0.07	0.257
VNI/SSCE	Student-t	-103.52	0.157	0.04	0.04	0.1	0.285
VNI/KOPSI	Student-t	-119.30	0.158	0.05	0.05	0.101	0.27
VNI/STI	Student-t	-116.49	0.151	0.057	0.057	0.096	0.259
VNI/TWII	Student-t	-116.61	0.152	0.052	0.052	0.097	0.268
During Covid 2020-2022							
VNI/SP500	Student-t	-10.9186	0.1185	0.0294	0.0294	0.0756	0.2636904
VNI/NIKKEN	Student-t	-32.53025	0.1003	0.0264	0.0264	0.0639	0.2727548
VNI/SSCE	Student-t	-32.53025	0.2594	0.0381	0.0381	0.167	0.2500388
VNI/KOPSI	Student-t	-37.90716	0.2696	0.0654	0.0654	0.1738	0.223592
VNI/STI	Student-t	-27.0519	0.2301	0.0609	0.0609	0.1478	0.2434203
VNI/TWII	Student-t	-15.6285	0.0836	0.057	0.057	0.0533	0.2820388
After Covid 2022-Now							
VNI/SP500	Student-t	-10.9186	0.0413	0.0014	0.0014	0.0263	0.2992699
VNI/NIKKEN	Student-t	-7.562396	0.1324	0.0002	0.0002	0.0639	0.2782151
VNI/KOPSI	Student-t	-34.05096	0.2848	0.0094	0.0094	0.1839	0.2472227
VNI/STI	Student-t	-25.12222	0.2162	0.0018	0.0018	0.1388	0.2466995
VNI/TWII	Student-t	-25.12222	0.2469	0.0058	0.0058	0.1589	0.2553981

Source: Author's calculations

Note: δ is the dependence coefficient; λ_L is the left-tailed dependence coefficient; λ_U is the right-tailed dependence coefficient; τ is the coefficient Kendall.

Table 3 analyzes the dependency of the Vietnamese stock market on global stock markets in low-volatility environments. Before the COVID-19 pandemic: Limited Reliance on International Marketplaces. During times of low volatility, the Student-t copula parameters show that the VNIndex, the Vietnamese stock market, moved in tandem with the major international stock markets of the US, Japan, South Korea, Singapore, China, etc.

Under calm conditions, the global financial markets did not substantially impact Vietnam's stock market, as indicated by the low dependency level ($\delta < 0.2$). Regional market integration was most evident in Vietnam's market, which was the most dependent on the stock markets of South Korea

and China. During this period, Vietnam was little affected by the severe declines in global markets, as seen by the lower tail dependency coefficient ($\lambda_L < 0.2$). Value at Risk (VaR95%) was 0.294 for the VNIndex/SP500 pair, the highest 100 investment possibilities. This means that under US market impact, losses in the Vietnamese market will not exceed 0.294 units in 95 out of 100 situations. Despite the generally minimal dependence, this indicates that the US market presented the greatest danger to investments in Vietnam.

During the COVID Era, the closer relationship between South Korea, China, and Singapore's stock market and Vietnam's stock market is proven by dependency coefficients ($\delta > 0.2$). A more robust impact of US financial circumstances on Vietnam was indicated by the notable increase in the dependence on the US stock market (SP500), which went from 0.04 to 0.1185.

In highly volatile market conditions

Table 4: Model parameter estimation results for Copula-GJR-GARCH In highly volatile market conditions

Before Covid 2007-2019							
Market	Copula	AIC	δ	λ_L	λ_U	τ	VaR 95%
VNI/SP500	BB7	-28.02852	1.05	1.502E-07	0.06	0.05	0.2939445
VNI/NIKKEN	BB8	-35.89561	1.307	0	0	0.078	0.2946284
VNI/SSCE	BB7	-93.55023	1.11	0.001	0.137	0.104	0.2812635
VNI/KOPSI	BB7	-104.5028	1.094	0.01	0.116	0.11	0.2483908
VNI/STI	BB7	-104.2828	1.08	0.0127	0.1095	0.114	0.2428014
VNI/TWII	Survival BB7	-107.4775	1.115	0.113	0.0036	0.113	0.2604557
During Covid							
VNI/SP500	BB7	-13.7926	1.1208	0.0004	0.144	0.1017	0.2757667
VNI/NIKKEN	JOE	-10.6331	1.1609	0	0.1832	0.0844	0.2957257
VNI/SSCE	Survival BB1	-93.55023	0.1726	0.1327	0.0268	0.1706	0.2546211
VNI/KOPSI	Survival Gumbel	-40.0924	1.2073	0.2244	0	0.1717	0.2290752
VNI/STI	BB7	-29.0454	1.0978	0.0676	0.1198	0.1554	0.2328943
VNI/TWII	BB8	-6.4808	1.2061	0	0	0.081	0.2932692
After Covid							
VNI/SP500	Survival Gumbel	1.0238	1.1208	0.032	0	0.0232	0.2932658
VNI/NIKKEN	BB8	-15.38383	1.8121	0	0	0.1543	0.2665207
VNI/KOPSI	BB8	-34.29146	2.0024	0	0	0.2163	0.2541549
VNI/STI	BB7	-27.45847	0.0555	0	0.1375	0.1269	0.2641895
VNI/TWII	BB8	-33.72586	2.1336	0	0	0.2194	0.2565543

Source: Author's calculations

Note: δ is the dependence coefficient; λ_L is the left-tailed dependence coefficient; λ_U is the right-tailed dependence coefficient; τ is the coefficient, Kendall.

Table 4 presents under conditions of extreme market volatility, the dependency structure between the US stock market and frontier stock markets is described through copula functions of the

Archimedean family (Clayton, Gumbel, Frank, Joe) and some mixed copulas (BB1, BB6, BB7, BB8). Based on the compared AIC values (excluding the Gauss and Student-t copula functions), the copula is most suitable for describing the dependency structure between the Vietnamese and international stock markets.

Discussion of Findings

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, the Copula family used the asymmetrical two-tails BB7 family to characterize the interdependence of the Vietnamese stock market with the US, China, Korea, and Singapore markets. When there is volatility on both sides of the trade war, such as when the markets in the US, China, Korea, and Taiwan experience a sudden downturn or upturn, Vietnam will follow suit. If the dependence coefficient is more significant in the lower (upper) tail, then there's a higher chance that the two markets will fall (rise) in price together. The VNI/SSCE pair has the most significant dependence coefficient in the upper tail at $\lambda_U=0.137$, which means that there's a 13.7% probability that the Vietnamese stock market will fall (rise) in price with the Chinese market (Zhang et al., 2021; Kartal et al., 2022).

In an upmarket, the Copula family says that the VNI/NIKKEN combination is BB8, which means that if the price of NIKKEN goes up, VNI will increase even more. As in the absence of highly volatile markets, the VNI/SP500 pair continues to have the highest VaR95% value during this time. In times of bad market conditions, the US financial market has a substantial influence on the frontier stock markets, according to this result and other prior research (Wang et al., 2023; Mohti et al., 2019; Chancharat & Chancharat, 2024). The dependence structure of the Vietnamese stock market and the US and Singapore markets during the Covid period is described by the Copula family as the BB7 family. This means that when both sides are volatile, there is a correlation.

Vietnam will react similarly when the US and Singapore markets fall (or rise) sharply. The VNI/SP500 pair has the highest tail dependence coefficient, with a value of $\lambda_U=0.144$, which is higher than in both the pre-and post-Covid periods (Otinga et al., 2024; Zuo, 2025; Gabauer, 2020; Alp et al., 2021). This confirms that during the epidemic period, the probability of the Vietnamese market booming or collapsing following the US market is higher than in other periods. The use of Copula Joe illustrates the interdependence of the Vietnamese and Japanese markets. There is a correlation between the two in times of falling markets; for example, there is an 18.32% chance that the Vietnamese market will have a higher degree when the Japanese market falls.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The authors present the following significant implications based on the extensive research findings in the previous section: When diversifying their portfolios, investors should consider how the Vietnamese stock market depends on other global stock markets. Determine the market hazards that influence the Vietnamese market using the value at risk. This will help you have adequate risk prevention strategies. Second, when the financial market is terrible, market managers and policymakers should be vigilant about the potential for many stock markets to collapse simultaneously. The potential for loss spreading throughout stock markets can be better understood, leading to the proposal of more adaptable measures aimed at stabilizing the financial sector.

Governments and central banks worldwide have reduced interest rates and increased the money supply as part of their economic stimulus programs to help businesses and individuals weather the COVID-19 crisis, leading to strong market growth. The significant standard deviation of stock indexes during this period compared to the other periods shows many potential risks of financial bubbles; however, the market grew rapidly due to a large cash flow into the market caused by production difficulties caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Global financial conditions, particularly those of the US, Japan, and China, are increasingly affected by Vietnamese stock prices. This study uses the Copula function and Monte Carlo simulations to show that market interdependence increases during the COVID-19 crisis. Vietnam's stock market was most exposed to US financial turmoil, although regional markets also mattered post-pandemic. Effective risk management, financial resilience, and macroeconomic cooperation are policy recommendations. Measures include diversifying investments, increasing derivative markets, and promoting financial awareness. Regulatory reform and regional collaboration can reduce external shocks. Stability requires a flexible exchange rate and effective budgetary policy. Promoting digital finance and green investments will support market growth.

Limitations and future research: Despite its value in assessing the Vietnamese stock market's dependence on international stock markets, this study has limitations: The Copula function-based Copula model assumes financial return series stationarity but incorporates nonlinear dependent structures. However, further studies can supplement high-frequency data analysis within day or hourly stock returns to highlight short-term dependencies and real-time market reactions to global events. The future of financial integration may depend on how long-term economic trends like digital transformation and green finance affect dependency structure.

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References

- Alp, O. S., Canbaloglu, B., & Gurgun, G. (2021). Stock liquidity, stock price crash risk, and foreign ownership. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 22(3), 477-486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2021.06.012>
- Aluko, O. A., & Kolapo, F. T. (2019). Macroeconomic factors and stock market development in sub-Saharan Africa: does the measure of stock market development matter? *Transnational Corporations Review*, 12(1), 53-62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2019.1683433>
- Arshad, R., Zada, H., Sohag, K., Wong, W. K., Ullah, E., & Raza, H. (2024). Does US monetary policy uncertainty affect returns of Asian developed, emerging, and frontier equity markets? Empirical evidence by using the quantile-on-quantile approach. *Heliyon*, 10(12), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e32962>
- Banda, K., Hall, J. H., & Pradhan, R. P. (2019). The impact of macroeconomic variables on industrial shares listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange. *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 12(3), 270-292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17520843.2019.1599034>
- Ciftci, I., Tatoglu, E., Wood, G., Demirbag, M., & Zaim, S. (2019). Corporate governance and firm performance in emerging markets: Evidence from Turkey. *International Business Review*, 28(1), 90-103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2018.08.004>

- Chancharat, S., & Chancharat, N. (2024). Asymmetric spillover and quantile linkage between the United States and ASEAN+ 6 stock returns under uncertainty. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 10(2024), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2024.100317>
- Chen, M. P., Chen, P. F., & Lee, C. C. (2014). Frontier stock market integration and the global financial crisis. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 29(2014), 84-103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.najef.2014.05.004>
- Cherubini, U., Luciano, E. & Vecchiato, W. (2004). *Copula Methods in Finance*. John Wiley & Sons, New Jersey. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118673331>
- Gabauer, D. (2020). Volatility impulse response analysis for DCC-GARCH models: The role of volatility transmission mechanisms. *Journal of Forecasting*, 39(5), 788–796. <https://doi.org/10.1002/for.2648>
- Glosten, L. R., Jagannathan, R., & Runkle, D. E. (1993). On the relation between the expected value and the volatility of the nominal excess return on stocks. *The journal of finance*, 48(5), 1779-1801. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1993.tb05128.x>
- Hasan, M., Mahi, M., Sarker, T., & Amin, M. (2021). Spillovers of the COVID-19 pandemic: Impact on global economic activity, the stock market, and the energy sector. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(5), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14050200>
- Joe, H. (1997). *Multivariate models and multivariate dependence concepts*. Chapman and Hall/CRC, London. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780367803896>
- Kartal, M. T., Ertuğrul, H. M., & Ulussever, T. (2022). The impacts of foreign portfolio flows and monetary policy responses on stock markets by considering COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence from Turkey. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 22(1), 12-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2021.06.003>
- Keswani, S., Puri, V., & Jha, R. (2024). Relationship among macroeconomic factors and stock prices: cointegration approach from the Indian stock market. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 12(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2024.2355017>
- Mohti, W., Dionísio, A., Ferreira, P., & Vieira, I. (2019). Contagion of the subprime financial crisis on frontier stock markets: A copula analysis. *Economies*, 7(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies7010015>
- Otinga, N. K., Obi, P., & Mugo-Waweru, F. (2024). Stock market participation puzzle: a systematic review and bibliometric analysis. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2396531>
- Thomas, N. M., Kashiramka, S., Yadav, S. S., & Paul, J. (2022). Role of emerging markets vis-à-vis frontier markets in improving portfolio diversification benefits. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 78(2022), 95-121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2021.11.012>
- Wang, Y., Wu, J., & Shi, Y. (2023). Stock index prediction using global market indices: A Granger causality-based graph representation learning method. *Procedia Computer Science*, 221(2023), 797-804. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2023.08.053>
- Zhang, P., Sha, Y., & Xu, Y. (2021). Stock market volatility spillovers in G7 and BRIC. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 57(7), 2107-2119. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1540496X.2021.1908256>
- Zuo, J. (2025). Impact of monetary policy on the stock market volatility: a GARCH-MIDAS approach in Malaysian economy. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 13(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2025.2459183>